

Sustain Sahel

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D2.2 Empirical model of constraints to the adoption of CSLP systems and practices

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Abbreviations

ANCAR	Agence Nationale de Conseil Agricole et Rural
AOPP	Association des Organisations Professionnelles Paysannes
CSLP	Crop-Shrub-Livestock-People
FMNR	Farmer-managed natural regeneration
ha	hectare
IP	innovation platform
M	Month
PI	Plateforme d'innovation
PRA	Participatory Rural Appraisal
RNA	Régénération Naturelle Assistée
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
WP	Work Package

Table of Contents

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	1
2 INTRODUCTION AND CONTEXT	3
3 METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH	4
4 KEY RESULTS	8
4.1 Socioeconomic profile of farmers.....	8
4.1.1 Distribution of producers by gender.....	8
4.1.2 Distribution of producers by marital status.....	8
4.1.3 Distribution of producers by level of education	9
4.1.4 Distribution of producers according to activities carried out.....	9
4.1.5 Farm equipment ownership	10
4.2 Modalities for integrating crop, livestock and shrubs/trees	11
4.2.1 Results of exchanges with producers	11
4.2.2 Results of the literature review	12
4.3 Gender perspectives of crop-shrub-livestock integration in the Sahel	15
4.3.1 Challenges to the adoption of CSLP systems	16
4.4 The empirical model of constraints to the adoption of CSLP systems	27
4.4.1 Component 1: Triggering conditions of CSLP adoption process	28
4.4.2 Component 2: The adoption process per se	30
4.4.3 Component 3: Performances and outcomes.....	31
5 CONCLUSIONS	32
6 REFERENCES	34
7 APPENDIXES	36
7.1 Appendix 1: Questionnaire for individual interviews with farmers	36
7.2 Guide d'entretien avec les personnels des services techniques (agriculture, élevage, foresterie)	42
7.3 Appendix 2: List of people involved in data collection and preliminary analysis...42	
7.4 Key shrubs and trees species used in CSLP systems in Saria sites.....	43

I Executive summary

The ability of integrated crop-livestock-shrub systems (CLSP) to effectively contribute to the improvement of agricultural resilience in the Sahelian zone depends on their effective adoption by producers in a context where adoption of agricultural technologies and innovations are reputed to be generally very low.

Based on data collected through interviews with variety of producers (youth, women, adults, herders, crop farmers) and other agricultural development professionals and a literature review, the main constraints to CSLP adoption were highlighted and analyzed. The analysis was done according to the specific components of the CSLP system, but also in a general way on the system as a whole.

This report presents the main socio-economic constraints to the adoption of CSLP systems. The analysis of these constraints, their mutual influences and interactions has allowed the development of an empirical model articulated in three main compartments: (i) the conditions of emergence of the demand; (ii) the conduct of the adoption process; and (iii) the results and their feedback on the first two compartments. The different compartments were characterized, and the determining factors and the extent of their influence on the adoption process were explained. That empirical model underlines the need to go beyond the focus on the innovation or the adopter and to give more consideration to the ecosystem approach to analyse and support adoption. In the remainder of the project, the different WPs would have to work in synergy under the joint leadership of WP2 (co-innovation and capacity development) and WP3 (adoption and scaling up) to effectively put in place and/or strengthen the ecosystem necessary for the adoption of CSLP technologies and innovations.

The results of this study on the constraints of CSLP systems are of great interest to all project's WPs, in particular WP 3, 4, 5, 6 and 8. For WP 3, which deals with adoption and scaling-up, the study provides data on the baseline situation, which can be used to analyze adoption dynamics, not only in terms of measuring the rate and intensity of adoption, but also and above all in analyzing the favorable conditions for the emergence and success of adoption processes. Adoption should not be analyzed solely from the perspective of the application of technologies by producers, but also from the perspective of the existence of conditions for the articulation of demand and supply, and the facilitation of the implementation of CLSP systems. For WP 4, 5 and 6, which mainly deal with the co-construction of innovations, the results of the study present two major interests. The first is methodological, highlighting the need for a holistic approach to innovation design and evaluation. This underlines the importance of close relations with innovation platforms, whose vocation is to mobilize and bring together the diversity of actors and stakeholders concerned by innovative systems. The second interest lies in the detailed knowledge of current constraints to adoption, and how to take these constraints into account in system co-construction processes. Finally, for the WP dealing with communication, including with strategic players, the results provide elements to fuel strategic dialogue and communication. In particular, they highlight the need for a global approach (innovation ecosystem) to support the adoption of CLSP systems, taking into account other stakeholders who facilitate the meeting of supply and demand and the supply of innovations for the development of CLSP systems.

D2.2 Empirical model of constraints to the adoption of CSLP systems and practices

To this end, the constraints highlighted by the technical services in relation to the integration of crops, trees and livestock and the factors to be taken into account to overcome the challenges were analyzed and will be taken into account in the implementation of the project. In addition, data on the overall environmental framework (policy) were analyzed, showing the existence of a policy that encourages concerted management of natural resources on a global scale.

The study was carried out on two sites, but the results are valid for the other project sites. These results will be presented within each innovation platform, enabling them to be adapted to the realities of each project site. Thus, at each project site, research will work with the platforms to find participatory solutions to the challenges of adopting integrated crop-tree-livestock systems.

The empirical model will be used to better plan actions linked to the co-design and dissemination of technologies. In this sense, the model will enable us to better understand the factors that can influence adoption, and to take the necessary measures at each level and according to the different actors to act positively on these factors in order to promote the adoption of technologies and innovations. The model could be used in the design of future projects and, above all, in the planning of project activities.

2 Introduction and Context

Farming practices and systems that integrate crops, livestock and shrubs or trees can contribute to strengthening the resilience of agropastoral systems and the livelihoods of rural populations in Sahelian zones. This would generate positive impacts on the fight against poverty (SDG1), climate change (SDG13), food security (SDG2) and land degradation (SDG15) among others. This premise is the basis of the SustainSAHEL project whose objective is to enhance the resilience and intensification potential of smallholder agricultural production systems to climate change through scalable innovations on crop, livestock, shrub (CLSP) integration. This outcome can only be achieved if relevant technologies and innovations based on CLSP systems are made more available and accessible. Most importantly, it is crucial that farmers actually adopt CLSP systems. Adoption is not understood here as a binary fact, but rather as an iterative and even reflexive process through which farmers make CSLP systems and practices as an element of their farm development strategy. The modalities of this process, and the nature and magnitude of its potential outcomes, may differ depending on the producers and the contexts.

Adoption rates of modern inputs or agricultural technologies, including some that are traditional such as agroforestry which is part of CSLP, crop rotations, and manure use, remain low (Arslan *et al.* 2022). A better understanding of the types of constraints, how they are influenced, and the consequences that follow is a major challenge for the SustainSAHEL project.

One of the main objectives of Deliverable D.2.2, is to build an empirical model that illustrates the constraints of adoption of CSLP, including the nature of these constraints and their consequences. The model is understood here in the sense of a simplified representation of the structures of a real phenomenon, the adoption of CSLP systems in this case, capable of explaining or dynamically reproducing its functioning. The construction of this representation includes, in particular, the identification of the components (or variables) of the phenomenon and, above all, the highlighting of the influential (or causal) relationships between these components (or variables).

This document is structured into three main sections. The methodological approach presents the process that was followed from data collection to the construction of the empirical model. The second section focuses on the results, with an emphasis on the profiles of producers, the modifications and constraints to adoption, and finally the empirical model resulting from the analysis of the different constraints and their influences. The third section presents conclusions and perspectives, particularly in the context of the development of the model.

3 Methodological approach

The method used included four main sequential steps as summarized in Figure 1. The first step consisted of framing and preparing the study. This involved defining the scope of the study, considering existing knowledge in the literature and the fact that WP3 had already carried out a similar activity in Mali and Senegal, but using a more econometric approach. The study protocol was developed, discussed and validated with the various members of WP2. The various data collection tools (questionnaires, interview guide, focus group discussion guide) were developed. Enumerators were mobilized and trained before being deployed in the field. This was to ensure that they were familiar with the objectives of the study and the data collection tools. This first stage of the study also involved engagement with relevant actors, particularly at the local level (farmer group leaders, technical, administrative and traditional authorities).

Figure 1. The four main steps of the study

The second step was the actual data collection, which was done at four scales: (i) the farm; (ii) the village / terroir; (iii) agricultural support services (extension, agrodealers etc.) and (iv) policy. summarizes the key themes that were covered during data collection. Three types of complementary activities were carried out in this regard. First, relevant scientific and technical literature and capitalization reports or grey literature (technical reports, project activity reports,

D2.2 Empirical model of constraints to the adoption of CSLP systems and practices

capitalization documents, etc.) on recent R&D projects on CSLP systems in the Sahel were reviewed with a focus on main constraints farmers faced in the implementation of CSLP systems.

Second, interviews were conducted with producers, acknowledging their diversity with respect to their starting point for the implementation of integrated CSLP systems. A distinction was made between producers whose main activity was crop production and those who were interested in livestock and the integration of shrubs or trees plants into their farms. The second category was livestock keepers integrating crops and shrubs/trees in his farm. Producers with a high density of trees on their farm and integrating crops and livestock formed the third category. In each of the three categories, there were sub-samples to take into account the possible specificities of youth and women. Data collection with producers was digitalized. The questionnaire was uploaded on the "kobo toolbox" platform. Enumerators used cell phones and tablets to complete the online questionnaire. In each of the two study sites, data was collected from a sample of 90 producers distributed as shown in the table below.

The third activity conducted for data collection consisted in the organisation of focus group discussions to complete the data, deepen the analysis and cross-check the information with the different categories of producers. Specific discussions were held with youth and women about the constraints they are facing in harnessing the potential of CSLP integration and their perceived related consequences on their farming practices and performances.

Data for this study were collected at the Saria (Burkina Faso) and Niakhar (Senegal). The decision to conduct data collection only in two of the seven project sites was motivated by the limited resources available, particularly for logistics. In addition, the choice to work only on two sites was also motivated by security constraints.

D2.2 Empirical model of constraints to the adoption of CSLP systems and practices

Box 1. Multi-scale analysis of factors that may affect the adoption of CSLP systems.

1. Farm
 - 1.1. Socioeconomic profile of the farmer
 - 1.2. Farm characteristics (different production activities, equipment,)
 - 1.3. Motivations and challenges for integrating CSLP
 - 1.4. Influence of Gender (specificities with regard to youth and women)
 - 1.5. Endogenous difficulties and solutions
2. Village/terroir
 - 2.1. Landscape
 - 2.2. Factors encouraging or hindering the adoption of CSLP systems
 - 2.3. Collective innovation or action to overcome constraints to the adoption of CSLP
3. Support services
 - 3.1. Availability
 - 3.2. Accessibility
 - 3.3. Quality
 - 3.4. Alignment or level of consideration of CSLP in the services provided
4. Policy/regulation
 - 4.1. Subsidy policies and other incentives
 - 4.2. Consideration and promotion of diversification and integration by agricultural policies
 - 4.3. Rules of access and management of collective resources related to CSLP

The third step was the analysis and interpretation of the data. The results obtained served for the preparation of the report (step 4), which was then consolidated through exchanges between the various actors involved in the preparation and implementation of the study.

Table 1. Sample size and composition for individual farmers surveys in each of the two sites of the study

Producer category	Total sample size	1/ Young farm leaders	2/ Women	3/ Men over 35 years)
A/ Farmer integrating livestock keeping and shrubs/trees farming	50	7	15	28
B/ Livestock keepers integrating crops and shrubs/trees in his farm	20	3	6	11
C/ Producers with a high density of trees on his farm and integrating crops and livestock	20	3	6	11
Total sample size	90			

D2.2 Empirical model of constraints to the adoption of CSLP systems and practices

The construction of the model started from the general and specific constraints (to the different components of the CSLP systems) identified by the different actors, notably the producers, but also the agricultural services. Data were collected on the causes of these constraints, their consequences, and the solutions already implemented or yet to be explored. Thematic blocks were identified, their relationships and possible influences were highlighted and used as a basis for the articulation of the empirical model.

4 Key Results

4.1 Socioeconomic profile of farmers

According to the results of the socio-economic profile analysis, the age of the growers varies from 17 to 74 years, with an average of around 43.5 years and an average standard deviation of 12.8 years. The level of education is generally low, with over 50% of growers having received no formal education. Interestingly, however, over 10% of growers have at least secondary education. Producers themselves recognize that low levels of education can be an obstacle to accessing and using certain information and knowledge for farming activities. The number of people on farms is quite high, averaging over 18. 20% of farms have more than 20 people.

4.1.1 Distribution of producers by gender

The survey was carried out among at least 189 growers on the two project sites, i.e. 27.5% women (see figure 2). The percentage of women varies from site to site. In Niakhar, 25.3% of respondents were women, while in Saria the figure was 29.8%.

Figure 2. Distribution of participants by gender

4.1.2 Distribution of producers by marital status

An analysis of producers' marital status reveals that they are single, married, divorced and widowed (figure 3)

Figure 3. Distribution of producers by marital status

All singles are men; in Niakhar, 17 of the 79 brides are women (21.5%) versus 21 in Saria (25.6%); in Saria, the divorcee is a woman, while in Niakhar it's a man; among the 14 widows/widowers, only one widower is in Niakhar.

4.1.3 Distribution of producers by level of education

Growers' level of education varies greatly overall, and even from site to site. The majority of growers on both sites have no education at all (figure 4). However, some growers on the Saria site even have a higher level of education.

Figure 4. Distribution of producers by education level

In Niakhar, among the 38 with no education level, 13 are women (34.2%), compared with 22 in Saria (42.3%); only one woman on each site has Koranic level; in Niakhar, among the 17 with literate level, 3 are women (17.6%), and in Saria there are no literate women; 4 women in Niakhar (20%) have primary school education, compared with 5 women in Saria (19.2%); 3 women in Niakhar have secondary school education (23.1%); in Saria, there are no women with secondary school education; the 3 people surveyed with higher education are all men.

4.1.4 Distribution of producers according to activities carried out

Farming and livestock breeding are the main activities of producers at both sites. Farming is the main activity for the majority of producers at both sites. However, a few producers at both sites have livestock farming as their main activity. The number of producers with livestock farming as their main activity is higher at Niakhar than at Saria (figure 5). Producers' secondary activities are mainly agriculture, livestock breeding, marachage, trade and handicrafts.

Figure 5. Distribution of producers according to activities carried out

22 women in Niakhar (24.7%) and 21 in Saria (29.2%) farm as their main activity; 2 women (50%) in Niakhar and 7 in Saria (31.8%) raise livestock as their main activity; 1 women (14.3%) in Niakhar and 7 in Saria (29.2%) farm as a secondary activity; 20 women (27.8%) in Niakhar and 17 in Saria (25.8%) engage in animal husbandry as a secondary activity; 2 women (28.6%) in Niakhar and 4 in Saria (19%) engage in market gardening as a secondary activity; the person who engages in crafts as a secondary activity at each site is a man; 5 women (35.7%) in Niakhar and 5 in Saria (100%) engage in commerce as a secondary activity.

4.1.5 Farm equipment ownership

Farm equipment ownership varies not only by type of equipment, but also by site. On the Niakhar site, for example, none of the growers owns a shelving unit, and on the Saria site, none of the growers owns a seed drill (figure 6). The main items of equipment available to farmers are ploughs, carts, wedges, seeders, ridgers, oxen and draught oxen, etc.

Figure 6. Distribution of farm equipment ownership

D2.2 Empirical model of constraints to the adoption of CSLP systems and practices

11 women in Niakhar (21.2%) and 15 women in Saria (21.4%) own a plough; 4 women in Niakhar (14.8%) and 1 women in Saria (8.33%) own a weeder; 0 women in Niakhar (0%) and 2 women in Saria (11.11%) own a weeder; 10 women in Niakhar (14.3%) and 10 women in Saria (22.22%) own a cart; 0 women in Niakhar (0%) and 3 women (30%) in Saria own a wedge ring; 11 women in Niakhar (16.4%) and 0 women in Saria (0%) own a seed drill; 0 women in Niakhar (0%) and 5 women in Saria (20.8%) own a sprayer; 0 women in Niakhar (0%) and 6 women in Saria (11.8%) own draught oxen; 15 women in Niakhar (30%) and 13 women in Saria (29.5%) own draught horses.

4.2 Modalities for integrating crop, livestock and shrubs/trees

CSLP are promoted as a mean of enhancing rural livelihood through sustaining provision of various products and ecosystem services. Interactions with farmers and results from literature review highlighted that there are CSLP systems may have different implementation modalities depending on the farmer, the socio-economic context or the enabling environment.

4.2.1 Results of exchanges with producers

4.2.1.1 Niakhar site in Senegal

❖ Focus group with farmers

Discussions with the focus group of farmers revealed that, overall, all the producers in the village (obviously all those in the focus group) adopt integrated crop, tree and livestock (CSLP) systems, but the rate of adoption of CSLP systems varies according to the technology used. For example, only producers with herds of oxen, goats or sheep use parkage. Around 20% of village producers use it. All producers in the village use composted or uncomposted manure spreading, crop association/rotation and RNA. Stabling (cattle and/or sheep fattening) is largely practiced by young people, who account for 20 to 30% of this category.

❖ Focus group with farmers

Discussions with the focus group of farmers revealed that CSLP systems are used by all village producers. In relation to the category of farmers in the focus group, the rate of adoption of CSLP systems varies according to the technology implemented. RNA, manure spreading and crop association/rotation are 100% adopted by the group category present. With regard to parking, only producers owning herds of oxen associated with goats or sheep implement it. According to the participants, only 10% of producers use it. Composting is practiced by at least 10% of producers in the village. Among the breeders present at the meeting, only 2% do so. Stabling (cattle and/or sheep fattening) is largely practiced by young people, who account for 20 to 30% of this category.

❖ Focus group with women

The main ways in which women integrate crop, tree and livestock systems are through reforestation, animal stabling on agropastoral plots, RNA and sustainable land management. The adoption rate of these technologies by the women's focus group was 75%, compared with a village average of 60%.

❖ Focus group with young people

The main ways in which young people integrate crop, tree and livestock systems are by parking animals in producers' plots, composting with cow dung and the droppings of certain animals, parking, reforestation during the rainy season and applying RNA and sustainable land management

(SLM) technologies. The rate of adoption of these technologies by the group of young people in the focus group was 100%, compared with a village average of 60%. However, this rate varies according to the different technologies (reforestation 15%, composting 70%, parking 40%, RNA and GDT 50%).

4.2.1.2 Saria site in Burkina Faso

15, 85% of the farmers questioned replied that they plant/maintain shrubs in their fields. For the 79 farmers who plant/maintain shrubs, the main motivations are: improving soil fertility (70), human food (67), animal fodder (39) and pharmacopoeia (43). Other motivations are diverse: i) the use of wood for fencing or cooking, ii) the fight against desertification, drought and erosion, iii) the establishment of living hedges.

The different species of birds and animals raised in the area are: poultry, goats, sheep, cattle, pigs and donkeys. Poultry farming is practiced by a large proportion of the population (86%). 77.4% of respondents practise livestock farming to improve soil fertility / manure production and 69.9% for financial reasons (savings and diversification of reviews).

4.2.2 Results of the literature review

Table 2 summarizes the main technologies and practices of CSLP system identified. Some key literature references that could be consulted for more information on the different practices are also provided. Key technologies identified include composting, fodder and forage production, Zai practice, life hedges/live fences, stabling/zero grazing and agroforestry parkland practice. Improved fallow when including animal grazing or feeding and crop rotation can also be considered. It is an agroforestry soil fertility technique. It has the potential to improve soil fertility by maintaining or increasing soil organic matter and biological nitrogen.

Table 2. Summary of integrated crop, shrub and livestock system commonly found in the Sahel

Technologies/Practices	Some bibliographic references
Manure application	Ayantunde et al., 2020; Kpadonou et al. (2017)
Mulched crop residues	Henderson et al. (2018); Kpadonou et al. (2017)
Farmer-managed natural regeneration (FMNR)	Zampaligré & Fuchs, 2019; Kpadonou et al. (2017); Camara et al. (2021)
Improved fallow	Etongo et al. (2018); Kaya (2000)
Use of fodders shrubs	Hamer et al. (2007)
Composting	Ayantunde et al., (2020) ; Zampaligré & Fuchs, 2019; Etongo et al. (2018); Somda et al. (2002); Kpadonou et al. (2017)
Fodder and forage production	Zampaligré & Fuchs, 2019
Zai practice	Etongo et al. (2018); Kpadonou et al. (2017)
Life hedges/live fences	Etongo et al. (2018); Levasseur et al. (2009); Levasseur (2004)

Stabling/ Zero grazing	Fisher et al. (2000); Ayantunde et al., (2020); Zampaligré & Fuchs (2019)
Agroforestry parkland practice	Augusseau et al. (2006); Belem et al. (2011); Petit (2003); Faye et al. (2010); Assé & Lassoie (2011)

Composting involves the production and use of organic matter extracted from crop residues, trees, shrubs, livestock manure and other household waste, usually to fertilize the soil. However, in the West African Sahel, this practice is mainly used by farmers who do not have livestock or with less, and in most cases crop residues are included in the compost. Fodders shrubs are cultivated by farmers to feed the livestock. Shrubs potentially grow rapidly and by the end of the first year are ready to be pruned for feeding to livestock. In addition, planting fodders shrubs does not involve any cash costs. Rather it allows farmers to substitute small amount of land and labour for cash.

Moreover, the living fences represent a model of integration of the tree in the agricultural and pastoral system. In practice, there are lines of trees or shrubs planted at the boundaries of farms, pastures, fields or animal pens. Living fences have multiple economic and ecological advantages. They provide fertilizer for the farmland. Leaves that fall naturally from the tree, as well as leaves and small branches cut off when the tree is harvested for fuel, can be (1) composted, (2) immediately mixed into the soil as a green manure, or (3) left on the ground as a leaf mulch. The leaves of many live fence species also provide nutritious forage for small animals. Other benefits are observed in medicine, material construction, trade, food consumption etc.

Parkland agroforestry, a system practiced by many local people, is very important for food security, microclimate improvement, income generation and environmental protection. Its roles are considered to be protective and place more emphasis on the sustainability of system services such as climate improvement, soil fertility improvement, wind erosion reduction, soil and water conservation, and environmental improvement. The productive roles of the system refer to the production of food, wood, shelter, fodder, manure, firewood and others, which are mainly goods needed to meet the basic needs of communities (Assé & Lassoie, 2011; Faye et al., 2010). Farmer-Managed Natural Regeneration (FMNR) is a practice commonly by farmer to initiate and/or strengthen the integration of trees and shrubs in their field.

If the modalities for developing CSLP systems are relatively variable, so too are those for integrating and/or consolidating its various components, as shown in Table 3. Producers choose the modalities according to their knowledge but also and above all according to their situation and objectives.

Table 3. Modalities for the integration or consolidation of CSLP components.

CSLP component	Modalities of integration or consolidation
Crops	Recovery of fallow land Crop rotation Association of crops (e.g. cowpea intercropped with millet, groundnut associated with cowpea and early millet associated with sanio millet) Integration of fodder crops Production of green manure

D2.2 Empirical model of constraints to the adoption of CSLP systems and practices

	Crop residues (millet stalks put in stacks that serve as fodder for livestock and as material for compost) Organic amendment Composting
Trees or shrubs	Famer managed natural regeneration (FMNR) with different species for soil fertility management, fodder or other virtues (human food, pharmacopoeia etc.) Arboriculture, establishment of orchards Community or private nursery Reforestation Tree planting Living hedge or fences Parklands
Livestock and animal husbandry	Stabling (cattle, sheep and goat fattening) Herd parking in some production fields Extensive breeding (movement of animals to pasture, transhumance) Manure application

4.3 Gender perspectives of crop-shrub-livestock integration in the Sahel

Data collected is consistent with the results of the literature review that there exist some gender roles that shape how women and men use and manage the different crop-shrubs-livestock integrated systems in the Sahel. There are significant differences in the ways women and men make use of the various CSLP technologies and systems. In particular, most of these differences stem from men's and women's access to and control over resources, the division of labour in the household, patterns of power and decision making, the responsibilities and local traditions and institutions.

Discussions during focus groups with women revealed that women use the same technologies as men. In this sense, technologies such as the production and use of organic manure, mulching, RNA, fattening, zaï and grass strips are used by both men and women. However, men and women do not have the same constraints when it comes to using these technologies. Women are limited in the use of these technologies by: lack of work force, insufficient technical skills, insufficient financial means to acquire the small equipment needed to implement these technologies, etc. For example, for zaï or organic manure production, women do not have the work force to support them in these activities, unlike men who use family labor, including women. Added to this is the lack of technical skills to implement these technologies. Few women have received capacity-building to carry out RNA or produce compost, unlike the men who are more often than not chosen from the families to take part in capacity-building sessions. In addition, there is a lack of financial means to acquire the equipment needed to implement these technologies, such as small equipment for organic manure production or zaï realization, as well as equipment for transporting manure to the field. Men have more access to such equipment than women.

It came out that technologies such as manure application, stabling/zero-grazing, and composting tend to have little or no impact on gender equity (Ayantunde et al., 2020). However, if we are to promote gender equity around these technologies, we may need to combine the use of these technologies with methodologies such as action learning centred on the farm household. Moreover, in the situation whereby women pastoralists already have long hours of workdays due to domestic chores, “stabling” practice, in particular, has been shown to increase the burdens of work on women. This is because the “stabling” practice requires a large family labour force, which leads women pastoralists to lose an important source of income (Fisher et al., 2000). Moreover, technologies such as compost production, manual application of manure, and mulching can increase labour demand, especially at the beginning of the rainy season when labour is in high demand for soil preparation, planting and weeding (Sissoko et al., 2022). Yet, women are more likely to face labour shortages than men in such periods.

Furthermore, limited land rights of women in the rural Sahel represent a critical issue in the implementation of technologies such as live hedge alongside its intensive labour requirement. Such conditions constrain the adoption of live hedges by the poorest farmers, women in particular. Already men are not willing to let women plant trees on their plots, because this could lead to conflicts when the inheritance is divided between children and different wives, depending on the case (Levasseur, 2004; Levasseur et al., 2009). The review also found few studies available on gender issues in the use of improved fallows practice. Belem et al. (2011) have indicated that improved fallows practice appears to be a gender-neutral practice. Despite the lack of evidence,

we still consider that there are opportunities to increase women's use of this technology. Besides, any development efforts towards the promotion of a crop-livestock-shrub/tree integrated system should consider the labour implications for both men and women. In addition, improving women's capacity and strengthening their access to economic resources (land, capital, and education) would be essential to enable them to play an active role and gain maximum benefit from the integration process.

4.3.1 Challenges to the adoption of CSLP systems

Constraints to the adoption of CSLP systems are numerous and variable (4). Some are specific to each of the components of the CSLP systems, i.e., crops, livestock, trees/shrubs, and to the producers themselves who implement and manage these systems. The frequency of constraints is relatively comparable across the two sites. Some constraints are more pronounced at some sites than at others. For example, the lack of livestock feed is more pronounced in Niakhar than in Saria. Furthermore, the different components of the CSLP system have varying degrees of specificity. However, other constraints are quite common, notably the issue of availability and access to agricultural services (inputs, advice, equipment). It appears that beyond the lack of awareness and the lack of capacity among producers, the issue of availability and accessibility to services is one of the major constraints.

Table 4. Frequency (% of producers) of main constraints hindering the integration of livestock, trees and shrubs into crop farming

Types of constraints		Niakhar	Saria
Difficulties in integrating livestock activities into crop and tree farming	Lack of feed (pasture, concentrates, etc.)	89	35
	Lack of knowledge about livestock management	40	44
	Conflicts with crop producers and lack of cattle tracks	27	28
	Insecurity and theft of livestock	28	8
	Unavailability and difficult access to veterinary and extension services	45	34
	Lack of financial means	30	22
	Unavailability of equipment (carts, tricycle, etc.) to transport manure	11	16
Constraints to the integration of trees and shrubs into livestock and crop farming	Unavailability of seeds and plants	63	56
	Lack of knowledge and skills on tree and shrub planting and maintaining	37	16
	High cost of seeds and seedlings	28	37
	Land insecurity or lack of land	10	10
	Competition with crops	12	43
	Destruction of plants by livestock	40	45
	Difficult access to technical advice and extension services	10	8
	Difficulty of mechanizing farming operations	21	17
	Inadequate and abusive pruning of young plants by herdsmen	10	8
Constraints for the development of crop farming	Insufficiency of agricultural extension advisory services	8	16
	Lack of manpower	10	18
	Lack of technical knowledge on crop management	15	22
	Unavailability of quality agricultural equipment and inputs (seeds, fertilizers, pesticides)	12	18
	Lack of saturation	14	6

4.3.1.1 Presentation of the results of discussions with farmers in Niakhar, Senegal

❖ Focus group with farmers in Niakhar

The main constraints, their consequences and the solutions proposed by the farmers' group are summarized in Table 5.

Table 5. Main constraints, consequences and solutions proposed by the farmers' group in Niakhar/Senegal

Main constraints Main	Main consequences	Solutions used or to be considered
Growing demographic population (increasingly important human capital)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insufficient arable land for everyone • Low Production • Food insecurity • Low farm income • Small crops relative to household size • Conflicts • Occupation of grazing areas • Lack of livestock grazing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intensification of organic amendments • Making the most of existing arable land potential
Soil poverty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lower yields • Less dense grass cover • Lack of forage, high feed costs • Producer poverty • Transhumance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Crop diversification • Assisted Natural Regeneration with local species • Amending farmland • Training producers in new technologies and good farming practices • Support for the acquisition of fertilizer species • Promotion of adapted early varieties and forage crops
Abusive cutting of shrubs and young shoots under RNA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sharp reduction in the number of trees • Disappearance of several species, especially traditional ones • Repression • Conflicts • Producer discouragement • Number of successful sub-RNA seedlings • Soil poverty • Rare rains • Unsuitable living environment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raising awareness among producers, breeders and women of households for sustainable management of natural resources • Setting up a framework for concerted management of natural resources • Strengthening of RNA activities, planting of new species adapted to the environment • Training producers on the importance of trees • Raising producers' awareness of the new forestry code • Making protective gabions
No village nursery due to freshwater problems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of plants • Difficulty of reforestation • No village woods • Difficult access to plants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support the creation of a village nursery • Train village nurserymen • Support the population with plants of various species

D2.2 Empirical model of constraints to the adoption of CSLP systems and practices

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Train growers in production, planting and reforestation techniques • Helping to develop a site
Difficulty of creating a full park in the medium term	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Security • Collecting cow dung for cooking • Conflicts • Transhumance • Animals running at large 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction of pens for small ruminants associated with oxen, and storage in pens • Training producers in composting techniques • Producing forage species • Intensive livestock farming • Impoundment
Difficult access to quality seeds and new technologies for good agricultural practices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low yield • Low income for producers • Rural exodus 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitating access to certified seeds • Train producers in good farming practices • Organizing village producers into a cooperative • Raising awareness of climate change among producers

❖ Focus group with farmers in Niakhar

The main constraints, their consequences and the solutions proposed by the group of breeders are summarized in Table 6.

Table 6. Main constraints, consequences and solutions proposed by the group of farmers in Niakhar/Senegal

Main constraints	Main consequences	Current solutions used or to be considered
Lack of grazing area	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parkland and reduced grazing area • Animals running at large • Conflicts • Transhumance • Livestock theft • Lack of forage • Short-term parking • Livestock roaming in freshly reforested areas, leading to the destruction of young plants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Updating the local agreement • Promoting forage crops • Set up livestock theft watch committees • Training producers in composting techniques • Set up wise committees to resolve internal conflicts • Delimiting livestock grazing areas
Salinization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction in arable land • Difficulty in regenerating certain harvested species • Reduced area under sowing • Salinity advances towards cropland 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reforestation with halophilic species • Organic amendment using peanut shells • Mineral amendment with phosphogypsum application • Development of anti-salt dykes, reservoir dykes
Lack of protective equipment for	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High mortality of RNA species 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support for the production of protective gabions

D2.2 Empirical model of constraints to the adoption of CSLP systems and practices

seedlings in the ground	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low success rate of RNA and plantations, especially in arboriculture • Conflicts • Producer discouragement • Number of successful sub-RNA seedlings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raising producers' awareness of the new forestry code • Making protective gabions
No village nursery due to freshwater problems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of plants • Difficulty of reforestation • No village woods • Difficult access to plants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support the creation of a village nursery • Train village nurserymen • Support the population with plants of various species • Train growers in production, planting and reforestation techniques • Helping to develop a site
Difficulty of creating a full park in the medium term	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Land security • Collecting cow patties for cooking • Conflicts • Transhumance • Animals running at large 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building pens for small ruminants associated with oxen and placed in yards • Training producers in composting techniques • Producing forage species • Intensive livestock farming • Impoundment
Difficult access to quality seeds and new technologies for good agricultural practices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low yield • Low income for producers • Rural exodus 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitating access to certified seeds • Train producers in good agricultural practices (production of organic manure, crop association and rotation, assisted natural regeneration, etc.). • Organizing village producers into a cooperative • Raising awareness of climate change among producers

❖ Focus group with women in Niakhar

The main constraints, their consequences and the solutions proposed by the women's group are summarized in Table 7.

Table 7. Main constraints, consequences and solutions proposed by the women's group in Niakhar/Senegal

Main constraints	Main consequences	Current solutions used or to be considered
Shortage of firewood	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tree pruning • Deforestation • 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of a community nursery • Promoting reforestation
Land degradation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lower yields • Increasing poverty 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compost making • Tree and livestock farming
Insufficient arable land	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poor integration of crops, trees and livestock 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tree cultivation and livestock association • Animal parking

D2.2 Empirical model of constraints to the adoption of CSLP systems and practices

Abusive tree cutting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The disappearance of certain species that fertilize the soil • Lower yields • More famine 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Setting up local agreements • Raising public awareness about improper tree cutting • Combination of tree crops and livestock • Creating community nurseries
Lack of grazing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decline in milk and meat production • Decline in the fertility of farmland 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promoting forage crops • Developing integrated crop, tree and livestock systems • Tree cultivation and livestock association

❖ Focus group with young people

The main constraints, their consequences and the solutions proposed by the women's group are summarized in Table 8.

Table 8. Main constraints, consequences and solutions proposed by the youth group in Niakhar/Senegal

Main constraints	Main consequences	Current solutions used or to be considered
Lack of pasture and grazing space	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Very difficult parking • Lack of fodder for livestock • Overexploitation of tree branches by herders to feed their animals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moving animals from one plot to another • Purchase of feed or straw for animals in dry periods • Existence of agreements within the community to reduce this type of practice.
Too high a density of trees in some fields	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business slowdown and mechanization difficulties 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tree care to reduce shading • Reducing tree density
Lack of forage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poor performance of draught animals at the start of the wintering season • High animal mortality in the dry season 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Purchase of livestock feed • Using crop residues to feed animals
High termite density in fields	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Destruction of crops and trees 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application of furadan (chemical product) • Application of drain oil to affected parts of trees • RNA
Land salinization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase in land unsuitable for agriculture • Lower yields 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Installation of anti-salt dikes • Use of manure (animal dung and cow dung) • Composting

4.3.1.2 Presentation of results of discussions with growers in Saria, Burkina Faso

Interviews with growers in Burkina Faso show that the main constraints to integrating trees into fields are: unavailability of seeds and seedlings, lack of knowledge and skills in planting and maintaining trees and shrubs, high cost of seeds and seedlings, insecure land tenure or lack of land, competition with crops, destruction of seedlings by livestock, difficult access to technical

D2.2 Empirical model of constraints to the adoption of CSLP systems and practices

advice and extension services, difficulties in mechanizing farming operations, inadequate and abusive pruning of seedlings by shepherds, etc.

❖ Focus group with farmers

The main constraints to integrating livestock into crop production activities are lack of knowledge about livestock management (43% of respondents), lack of feed (31.2%), and conflicts with farmers (28%). These constraints are linked to those mentioned under other constraints, including animal mortality, epizootics and lack of shelter. Added to this is difficult access to veterinary and livestock services (18.3% of respondents), insecurity / theft of livestock (11.8%), lack of financial means (15.1%), lack of pasture (11.8%).

❖ Focus group with farmers

In terms of the main constraints, farmers pointed to difficult access to agricultural advice, lack of manpower, lack of technical knowledge for agricultural activities, unavailability of inputs (seeds, fertilizers, etc.), conflicts with farmers, lack of land, epizootic diseases among poultry and small ruminants.

❖ Summary of constraints and proposed solutions to Saria's challenges

Faced with the challenges of systematically integrating crops, trees and livestock, farmers are experimenting with endogenous solutions to overcome the challenges, but have also noted the need for external support. Table 8 summarizes this situation.

Table 9. Endogenous solutions and expected external support to overcome the challenges of integrating crops, trees and livestock.

	Main difficulties encountered	Producer solutions	Types of external support expected
Livestock integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of livestock and poultry feed: • Lack of grazing • Lack of cattle tracks • Lack of knowledge about livestock management • Lack of livestock infrastructure and equipment • Insecurity / cattle rustling • Animal diseases: Epizootics, infectious diseases, local treatments are increasingly ineffective 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Straw and crop residue conservation • Use of aerial forage for herbivores • Construction of makeshift housing • Letting animals roam in search of food • Treatment of animals with traditional pharmacopoeia : • Tree bark for poultry care • Put kouka bark in water and feed it to poultry. • Tree roots • Tree roots to care for chicks • Health prophylaxis • Quarantine the sick • Take care of your animals' health by using pharmacopoeia products 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capacity building on • breeding management, • animal health, • food manufacturing • Subsidy : • infrastructure, • equipment, • vaccines, • animal feed • Improving vaccine quality • Feed aids for animals • New breeds added • Donating laying hens • Contribution of incubators, feed

D2.2 Empirical model of constraints to the adoption of CSLP systems and practices

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reducing production • Approach with technicians • Isolate sick animals 	
Integration of agriculture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of technical knowledge for agricultural activities • Unavailability of inputs (seeds, fertilizers, etc.) • Lack of land • Lack of agricultural equipment • Compost • Soil poverty • Rare rains • Weed invasion 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compost production • Use of organic manure • Live construction • Land negotiation • Preserving old varieties • Rental of agricultural production equipment • Soil fertilization with crop residues and tree leaves (mulching) • Sprayed fields 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capacity-building in integrated system production techniques • Subsidies for inputs, equipment and improved seeds • Support for agricultural inputs and equipment • Financial resources • Follow-up support to ensure real beneficiaries • Appropriate equipment for agriculture
Integrating shrubs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Destruction of plants by animals • Lack of technical knowledge of shrub planting and maintenance • Lack of water for plant maintenance • Rare rains • Soil poverty • Plants die 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Protecting shrubs with fencing • Living hedge • Tree care • Tree planting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reforestation • Fencing of the agricultural production site • Reforestation training • Giving growers lots of trees • Capacity building • Borehole construction

4.3.1.3 Presentation of the results of discussions with the technical agricultural advisory services at the two sites

Discussions were held with rural development technical agents (agriculture, livestock and environment) at the Saria and Niakhar sites. Table 10 summarizes the results of these exchanges.

Table 10 : Summary of constraints and proposed solutions to overcome challenges, according to technical services

Technical Services	Constraints to the adoption of CSLP systems	Proposed solutions to CSLP system integration challenges
Agriculture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The physical pollution of the environment, in particular the presence of a lot of plastic waste when manure is spread; • Animals running at large • Abusive cutting of young plants for most fertilizer species 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set up local agreements and ensure compliance with the rules, on pain of severe penalties. • Training and awareness-raising for the local population • Implement assisted natural regeneration (ANR) and reforestation of certain fertile species

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set up village committees to ensure compliance with measures and safeguard the forest heritage • Create village nurseries and set up watch committees • Set up grazing areas to prevent animals from straying • Encourage crop/tree/livestock combinations
Breeding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of land • Soil poverty • Outdated farm equipment • Difficult access to feedstuffs • Insufficient grazing areas and water points • Abusive tree cutting • Plant tracking problems • Destruction of plants during cultivation operations • Non-demarcation of livestock grazing areas 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training and awareness-raising for the local population • Revitalizing local natural resource management agreements • Setting up zonal cooperatives • Favoring forage crops • Setting up community nurseries • Park animals to produce organic manure • Promote RNA and reforestation with local fertilizing species • Controlling insect pests such as the "Kadd" on fertilizer trees
Environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Abusive logging; • Divagation of animals that destroy young plants • The narrowness of livestock rangelands is often a problem, especially as grazing areas are almost non-existent, leading herders to seek out pasture by practicing extensive livestock farming (transhumance). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RNA and reforestation, not forgetting the multiplication of village nurseries • Raising producers' awareness of climate change ; • Train growers in technologies for adapting to the effects of climate change (mulching, use of organic manure, zaï, use of improved seeds, etc.). • Create well-defined and fenced grazing areas to stabilize transhumant animals.

4.3.1.4 Level of political commitment to promoting integrated crop-tree-livestock systems

❖ Political action in favor of integrated crop-tree-livestock systems in Senegal

In Senegal, the integration of crops, trees and livestock is considered a major political issue. To this end, texts and/or approaches have been drawn up or supported by the State through its agencies. A case in point are local conventions, an emerging issue in the shared management of natural resources in Senegal. These conventions are designed to promote rational regulation of access to and use of resources, as well as effective management of conflicts arising from competition between users for their control (Djiré and Dicko, 2007). Local conventions include: (i) land-use plans, (ii) irrigated area charters, (iii) environmental action plans, (iv) local development plans, (v) forest management plans. These are "negotiated" local management practices based on consultation. In Senegal, local agreements are governed by the texts of the decentralization reform. Their formulation, implementation and monitoring remain the prerogative of rural communities.

D2.2 Empirical model of constraints to the adoption of CSLP systems and practices

Discussions with the technical departments show that the policy supports a great deal of action in the field to promote natural resource management, i.e. to promote the integration of crops, trees and livestock. This is the case for:

- awareness-raising and capacity-building on ANR and reforestation ;
- demarcation of livestock rangelands for peaceful cohabitation between farmers and herders;
- the parking of animals in fields;
- raising awareness of animal vaccination and organizing annual group vaccinations, subsidized by the government;
- support for local authorities in implementing local agreements;
- setting up livestock feed storage warehouses, subsidized by the Senegalese government; etc.

With the support of the State through the Ministry of the Environment, advocacy has been made for the implementation of national and sub-regional programs for the sustainable management of natural resources. These include

- the local governance and decentralized natural resource management project (GL-GDRN). This project was initiated by the Centre de suivi écologique (CSE) in partnership with the International Development Research Centre (IDRC, Canada). This program was designed to build the capacity of local elected officials in natural resource management;
- the "Negos-GRN" program: Managing the territory's natural resources together, which was implemented in Senegal, Mali and Burkina Faso and produced the "Guide méthodologique pour promouvoir et consolider une gestion négociée des ressources naturelles en Afrique de l'Ouest" (Methodological guide to promoting and consolidating negotiated natural resource management in West Africa).

There is also a legal framework for natural resource management in Senegal, based on political guidelines. Political guidelines for natural resource and land management in Senegal include

- the National Environmental Action Plan (PNAE);
- the National Action Plan to Combat Desertification ;
- the National Forestry Program;
- the Agro-Sylvo-Pastoral Orientation Law (LOASP);
- the sectoral environmental policy letter;
- the strategy for implementing the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change; etc.

❖ **Political action in favor of integrated crop-tree-livestock systems in Burkina Faso**

In Burkina Faso, as in Senegal, the issue of integrating crops, trees and livestock is taken into account by politicians as a major challenge. To this end, texts and/or approaches have been drawn up or supported by the State through its agencies.

D2.2 Empirical model of constraints to the adoption of CSLP systems and practices

Discussions with technical departments show that policy-makers are supporting many actions in the field to promote natural resource management, and hence the integration of crops, trees and livestock. This is the case for:

- awareness-raising and capacity-building on ANR and reforestation ;
- demarcation of livestock rangelands for peaceful cohabitation between farmers and herders;
- raising awareness of animal vaccination and the annual organization of group animal vaccinations, subsidized by the State;
- subsidizing production inputs;
- setting up livestock feed storage warehouses with state subsidies; etc.

In addition, the Burkinabe government, through the Ministry of the Environment, advocates the implementation of national and sub-regional programs for the sustainable management of natural resources.

Examples include:

- the Programme d'appui au secteur forestier (PASF), jointly developed by the Luxembourg Cooperation and the Government of Burkina Faso, with a view to supporting the management of Burkina Faso's forestry resources, using a coherent and coordinated sectoral approach within the framework of the Programme national du secteur rural. Implemented by LuxDev and the services of the Ministry of the Environment, Green Economy and Climate Change (MEEVCC), the program drew on existing national procedures and structures for its implementation;
- the Projet de Gestion participative des Ressources Naturelles et de Développement rural au Nord, Centre Nord et Est (NEER-TAMBA Project), a category B project designed by the International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD) and the Government of Burkina Faso in line with the country's broad socio-economic development guidelines;
- the "Negos-GRN" program: Managing the territory's natural resources together, which has been implemented in Senegal, Mali and Burkina Faso, and which has drawn up a "Methodological guide to promote and consolidate negotiated natural resource management in West Africa"; etc.

In addition, there is a legal framework for natural resource management in Burkina Faso, based on political guidelines. Political guidelines for natural resource and land management in Burkina Faso include the following:

- National environmental policy;
- the local code for the management of local resources;
- LAW N°006-2013/AN on the environmental code in Burkina Faso, which aims to protect living beings against harmful or inconvenient effects and risks that hinder or endanger their existence due to the degradation of their environment, and to improve their living conditions.
- the 2007 national environmental policy document: this national environmental policy was adopted in 2007 by decree (2007-160). The issues at stake are political ('sustainable development'), economic ('the contribution of natural resources to the economy'), social ('the enhancement of local knowledge, which plays a key role in preserving biodiversity'), educational (building an 'environmental ethic, the basis of eco-citizenship') and cultural ('the spiritual aspects of different interest groups');

D2.2 Empirical model of constraints to the adoption of CSLP systems and practices

- the 2002 law on pastoralism, which sets out the principles and procedures for the sustainable, peaceful and integrated development of pastoral, agropastoral and sylvopastoral activities;
- Decree no. 410 of 2007: conditions of allocation, occupation and use of managed pastoral zones, which provides further details on access to and use of zones managed by the State and local authorities. A managed pastoral zone (ZPA) is a group of rural lands, demarcated and managed by the State or local authorities for livestock and animal production activities, whether or not in association with plant and/or forest production; etc.

4.4 The empirical model of constraints to the adoption of CSLP systems

The analysis of constraints to the adoption of CSLP practices and systems has made it possible to develop an empirical model that enable the visualization of different actors involved in adoption processes as well as the existing relationships between them. This model, represented in Figure 11, includes three main components: (i) triggering conditions of CSLP adoption process, (ii) the adoption process itself, and (iii) the results and effects induced by adoption.

Figure 11. Empirical model of constraints to the adoption of CSLP systems

The three components are not at all isolated, they influence and interact with each other. Thus, the demand process is triggered in the concretization of the demand and the different elements that characterize it. The results should not be seen only because of the adoption process followed. The results obtained are of a nature to determine the demand. The intensity and rate of adoption can only increase if the enabling conditions allow it, but also and especially if the results generated by the adoption are globally positive. Moreover, the quality of the results obtained is strongly influenced by the way in which the adoption process was conducted.

4.4.1 Component I: Triggering conditions of CSLP adoption process

This refers to the favorable or constraining conditions for the birth and emergence of the idea of adopting one or more components of CSLP systems. This compartment is based on the fact that the demand responds to a specific need that may be clearly expressed or latent. This need depends on the actual or potential supply of CSLP technologies and innovations, but also on the potential involvement of support and facilitation services that can contribute to the formulation of demand, but also to the strengthening of supply and to a match between supply and demand. The compartment “Conditions for the emergences of the emergence of the demand” is made up of three subsystems: Demand, supply and, facilitation, support and incentive services.

4.4.1.1 Sub-component 1: The demand

This component includes, on the one hand, producers characterized by their socioeconomic profile, their level of sensitivity to the integration of CSLP systems, but also and above all their plans or motivation for adopting CSLP systems. The surveys and focus group discussions showed that these motivations could be multiple, ranging from soil fertility management to improved food security and income diversification.

Producers resources of production means influence their decisions and practices. For example, in the livestock component of the CSLP systems, it appears that young people and women, and more generally producers with limited financial resources, are primarily interested in poultry and small ruminants (sheep, goats), whose prices are generally more accessible than those of cattle. Producers with limited equipment or means of transporting organic manure will opt more for in situ green manure production solutions. In some cases, low resource availability may be a factor in the adoption of CSLP systems. When producers have small land areas, they tend to practice mixed farming and seek other means of income diversification, including livestock or tree farming. Overall, the influence of the demand sub-component is determined by three main factors: farmer profile and capacities, means of production, expected benefits from CSLP systems, and the level of integration of the farmer in socio-professional networks related to CSLP systems and agricultural development in general. Peer-to-peer exchanges are very high in rural areas and are often one of the main means of disseminating information and technology.

4.4.1.2 Sub-component 2: The supply

This component is about the existing CSLP technologies, innovations and the inputs necessary for their valorization. It includes the different species of plants, trees and shrubs, and domestic animals adapted to the local agro-climatic context. The existing CSLP technologies, innovations and related inputs necessary for implementation are considered as relevant only if they are in

D2.2 Empirical model of constraints to the adoption of CSLP systems and practices

line with the expressed or latent/potential demand of producers. The parameters that determine the extent and modalities of influence of supply on CSLP adoption are:

- i. **Availability:** can the technology, innovations and related inputs be found locally or in the neighboring village or town without having to make a difficult trip?
- ii. **Accessibility/affordability:** are the technologies and inputs financially and socially accessible to all categories of interested farmers?
- iii. **Quality:** Are available CSLP technologies, innovations and related inputs reliable? Would they generate the desired results if used correctly?
- iv. **Information:** Is information about the technologies, innovation and inputs available and accessible?

4.4.1.3 Sub-component 3: Facilitation, support and incentivizing services

This sub-component is composed of actors involved in facilitating, supporting and/or providing incentives for the successful CSLP system adoption processes. These services are designed to help producers seize opportunities (access to markets, etc.) but also to overcome constraints related to CSLP systems (contact with veterinary services, producers of seeds and seedlings of forest species, etc.). They also include actors which intervene in capacity building and regulation and service delivery at local and national levels. These services play an important role in raising awareness among producers, but also in supporting their adoption of CSLP systems. This support can take the form of support for the acquisition of inputs through partial or total subsidies, the provision of technical advice, facilitation of access to relevant knowledge and innovations requested by producers.

Their actions can be direct, as in the case of subsidizing seeds and seedlings or breeding cores, or indirect, as in the case of charters and/or regulations governing the management of natural resources. Four main characteristics of facilitation, support and incentive services influence adoption processes:

- a) **Availability:** the existence of services within a radius that is easily accessible to producers. This may include the availability of extension services. Interviews showed that agricultural advisory services related to crop production are more available than those related to livestock or to tree farming. Moreover, extensionists are often very specialized in particular field or CSLP component and don't have enough knowledge on the other components, hence they are not well equipped for the promotion of an integrated technologies like CSLP.
- b) **Accessibility:** accessibility is the cost that producers must incur to access services. This may include the cost of purchasing seeds, young animals for breeding
- c) **Quality:** this is a composite indicator that refers to the capacity to effectively respond to demand with reliability, relevance and consistency with the problems posed by producers and in a timely manner.
- d) **Modalities of relationships with producers:** this parameter is important to ensure that the services provided are effectively in line with the needs and situation of producers. This modality also influences accessibility

D2.2 Empirical model of constraints to the adoption of CSLP systems and practices

- e) **Alignment:** refers to the coherence between producers' demands and the offer of facilitation services in terms of technologies and innovations for the implementation of CSLP systems.

4.4.2 Component 2: The adoption process per se

The most important thing for producers is not to start the adoption process, but to be able to conduct it efficiently so as to maximize the chances of obtaining the desired results. This second component of the empirical model reflects this principle. In fact, the adoption process itself is considered to include iterations and learning that may lead producers to adjust their choices based on new information and/or preliminary lessons emerging from the application of CSLP systems. This Component on adoption per se has three main sequential elements that influence each other. These are: (i) awareness, knowledge and ongoing capacity development; (ii) informed choice of system components; and (iii) implementation, adaptive management and system strengthening.

- i. *Awareness, knowledge and capacity development:*
 - Awareness: Level of awareness about the potential benefits and challenges of CSLP systems. This awareness can be achieved through learning from peer producers, but also through the support of extension and advisory services
 - Knowledge: level of technical and organizational knowledge about the components of CSLP systems and how they are managed
 - Capacity renewal: continuous renewal of the capacities needed by producers to manage challenges and opportunities emerging from the application of CSLP systems
- ii. *Sound selection of different components of the CSLP system:*
 - Level of technical and functional consistency in the combination of modalities of the different components of the CSLP systems.
 - Level of coherence between the type of CSLP system chosen and the objectives sought by the producer through adoption
- iii. *Implementation, adequate management and consolidation of the CSLP systems:*
 - Adherence to recommended technical management system of the selected CSLP system
 - Ability to take appropriate tactical actions to manage challenges emerging from the implementation of the CSLP system; including through analysis of preliminary results, exchanges with other producers and with extension services;
 - integration of complementary measures to strengthen the functioning and performance of the CSLP systems (e.g. introduction of fodder plants to strengthen livestock development, acquisition of carts to transport compost to the fields, etc.).

The level of awareness and knowledge largely determines the choice of component modalities and the combination pattern. This combination must be consistent with the specificities of the

chosen modalities, but also with the producers' objectives. Preliminary results from the implementation of the CSLP system may lead producers to seek new knowledge and/or develop new capacities. This is the case, for example, when it is necessary to manage the density of shrubs or trees in the fields to avoid competition with crops.

4.4.3 Component 3: Performances and outcomes

Performance reflects the level of achievement of producers' expectations when they engage in the process of adopting CSLP systems. These goals may refer to improved food security, farm income, or conditions. Performance is important in adoption processes. It is important that results live up to expectations and, if possible, arrive within a short time frame. For example, some farmers have expressed a reluctance to use species that take a long time to mature (e.g., baobab, *Faidherbia*). The influence of performance and outcomes on adoption is determined through the following four variables:

- i. Payback period: number of months or years before the farmers starts yielding the benefits
- ii. Magnitude of the benefits: are the results and outcomes of the adoption of CSLP up to the expectations of the farmers?
- iii. Diversity of benefits: how many of benefits are generated by CSLP systems adopted? Producers tend to prefer technologies that generate a diversity of benefits than those that yield only one type of benefits, exp: a shrub or tree species that can produce fodder for livestock feeding while also contributing to soil fertility and feeding of the household will be preferred to those that contribute only to soil fertility
- iv. Cost/benefit: do the benefits generated by compensate the cost incurred (labour, other expenses e.g. inputs etc.)?

Moreover, performance provides feedback to the other components of the model. The analysis of the performance obtained may lead: (i) the producer to review the management of his farm including the configuration of CSLP system and related practices, (ii) the facilitation services to review the quality of their interventions, and (iii) to examine the characteristics of the supply in order to carry out some adjustments if deemed necessary.

5 Conclusions

This deliverable provides knowledge on the main challenges and constraints that hinder the adoption of the different components, but also the CSLP system as a whole. The empirical model of adoption developed from the surveys with farmers, extensionists and other agricultural development actors provides a good visualization of the different factors, but also shows how they interact and condition the progress and success of CSLP adoption process.

This model emphasizes that the adoption process is triggered by the interaction between three major groups of factors or components: Demand, Supply and Facilitation, Incentive and Support Services. The Demand component through, the producers and the characteristics of their production system and the purposes motivating the adoption are fundamental. However, the "Facilitation services" component has an instrumental role, because it contributes not only to the strengthening of Demand and Supply, and their adequacy, but also and above all, it accompanies the adoption process that arises from the modalities of the meeting of demand and supply of technologies, innovations and related inputs. Facilitation services play a more decisive role than supply.

Focus groups and other interactions conducted during data collection activities were an opportunity to engage in dialogue and allowed producers to share their concerns, but also good practices and elements of strategy to address the challenges to the adoption of CSLP systems. It appeared that there are some endogenous solutions but that are yet not well known in the community. The promotion of CSLP should integrate more collective dynamics and learning to remove constraints to adoption processes. The establishment and efficient facilitation of Farmer field schools around CSLP could be interesting to operationalize this dynamic. In addition to the constraints specific to each of the components of the CSLP system, the study highlighted the crucial role of agricultural services in facilitating producer awareness, building their capacities, and supporting their adoption of CSLP systems.

It is suggested that the empirical model be used to establish the baseline situation at the various project sites. A scoring tool could further develop to facilitate its use, for baseline but also to assess the progressive results of the project in tackling adoption constraints. When using the empirical model and its related scoring tool once developed, particular attention would have to be paid to the information contained in the various components of the model. But beyond data collection, the emphasis should be on dialogues between the different stakeholders. In addition, the model developed can also be used to prepare for the dissemination of CSLP technologies and best practices that emerge from the project, so as to anticipate or consider challenges. It would be useful for project members working on the design or development of technologies to consolidate the choice for a systemic approach and to keep in mind the constant concern for the conditions necessary for adoption. Finally, the empirical model underlines the need to go beyond the focus on the innovation or the adopter and to give more consideration to the ecosystem approach to analyze and support adoption. In the remainder of the project, the different WPs would have to work in synergy under the joint leadership of WP2 (co-innovation and capacity development) and WP3 (adoption and scaling up) to effectively put in place and/or strengthen the ecosystem necessary for the adoption of CSLP technologies and innovations.

D2.2 Empirical model of constraints to the adoption of CSLP systems and practices

The results of this study on the constraints of CSLP systems are of great interest to all the project's WPs in particular WP 3, 4, 5, 6 and 8. For WP 3, which deals with adoption and scaling-up, the study provides data on the baseline situation, which can be used to analyze adoption dynamics, not only in terms of measuring the rate and intensity of adoption, but also and above all in analyzing the favorable conditions for the emergence and success of adoption processes. Adoption should not be analyzed solely from the perspective of the application of technologies by producers, but also from the perspective of the existence of conditions for the articulation of demand and supply, and the facilitation of the implementation of CSLP systems. For WP 4, 5 and 6, which mainly deal with the co-construction of innovations, the results of the study present two major interests. The first is methodological, highlighting the need for a holistic approach to innovation design and evaluation. This underlines the importance of close relations with innovation platforms, whose vocation is to mobilize and bring together the diversity of actors and stakeholders involved in innovative systems. The second interest lies in the detailed knowledge of current constraints to adoption, and how to take these constraints into account in system co-construction processes. Finally, for the WP dealing with communication, including with strategic players, the results provide elements to fuel strategic dialogue and communication. In particular, they highlight the need for a global approach (innovation ecosystem) to support the adoption of CSLP systems, taking into account other stakeholders who facilitate the meeting of supply and demand and the supply of innovations for the development of CSLP systems.

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7 Appendixes

7.1 Appendix I: Questionnaire for individual interviews with farmers

SustainSAHEL

« Analyse des contraintes à l'adoption des systèmes intégrés cultures-arbustes-élevage en zone sahélienne »

Les informations recueillies resteront confidentielles. Elles ne seront utilisées qu'à des fins de recherche-action pour la promotion des systèmes intégrés cultures-arbustes-élevage en zone sahélienne d'Afrique de l'Ouest

Site :
Numéro de la fiche

I/Généralités

Tableau I

Date de l'enquête :	Nom enquêteur :
Pays	Commune / District
Village :	Quartier :

I/I Caractéristique socio-économique du producteur

Tableau 2

Nom et prénom de l'enquêté :	Age (ans) :
------------------------------	-------------

I/I.1 Sexe : 1) Masculin ; 2) Féminin

I/I.2. Langue : _____

I/I.3 Origine: 1) Autochtone; 0) Allochtone

I/I.4 Religion : Musulman...1 ; Chrétien...2 ; Animiste...3 ; Autre...4 :

I/I.5 Situation matrimoniale : Marié (e)...1 ; Célibataire...2 ; Veuf/Veuve...3 ; Divorcé (e)... 4

I/I.6 Niveau d'instruction le plus élevé : Aucun...1 ; Alphabétisé...2 ; Primaire...3 ; Coranique...4 ; Secondaire...5 Supérieur...6

I/I.7 Activité principale : Agriculture (productions végétales).....1; Élevage ...2 ; Artisanat...3 ; Commerce...4 ; Orpaillage...5 ; Autres (à préciser).....6 :

I/I.8 Activités secondaires (plusieurs réponses possibles): Aucune...1 Agriculture...2 ; Élevage...3 ; Artisanat...4 ; Commerce...5; Orpaillage...6 Maraîchage ;...7 Autres (à préciser)...8

I/I.9 Nombre de personnes vivant au sein de l'exploitation agricole : _____ Hommes ; _____ Femmes

I/I.10 Nombre d'actifs dans l'exploitation agricole : _____ Hommes ; _____ Femmes

I/2 Tenure foncière et niveau de fertilité des sols

I/2.1 Mode d'accès au foncier : Héritage1 ; Achat...2 ; Don...5 ; Location...3 ; Prêt...4 ; Métaillage...5

I/2.2 La superficie totale : En propriété (ha) : _____ ; Pris en location : _____ ; Pris en prêt : _____ ; Pris en Métaillage _____

I/2.3 La superficie cultivée (ha) : En 2021 : _____

Niveau de fertilité des sols : Proportion de terre (%)..... Très fertile ;Fertiles ;Moyennement Fertile ;Faiblement Fertile ; Non Fertile ;Inculte.

I.3. Équipements agricoles

1) Charrue : _____ ; 2) Corps sarcler : _____ ; 3) Corps butteur : _____ ;

4) Charrette : _____ ; 5) Rayonneur : _____ ; 6) Semoir : _____ ;

7) Pulvérisateur : _____ ; 8) Tracteur : _____ ; 9) Bœufs de trait : _____ ;

10) ânes de trait : _____ ; 11) Autres : _____

2/ Caractéristiques des différents ateliers

2.1 Atelier Productions végétales

2.1.1 Quelles sont les principales cultures pratiquées au cours de la campagne agricole 2021 (compléter le tableau ci-après)

Cultures	Superficie (ha)
Sorgho	
Petit Mil	
Maïs	
Riz	
Niébé	
...	
...	

2.2. Productions animales

2.2.1 L'exploitant pratique-t-il l'élevage ? Oui Non

2.2.1.1. Si oui cheptel (nombre) :

Espèces	Cheptel actuel (nombre)
Volailles	
Caprins	
Ovins	
Bovins	
Porcins	
Asins	
Autres (à préciser)	

2.2.1.2 Quelles sont les motivations pour la pratique de l'élevage ?

- | | |
|---|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Amélioration de la fertilité des sols / production de fumier | <input type="checkbox"/> Mécanisation des travaux agricoles et transport des intrants ou récoltes |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Valorisation des résidus de cultures | <input type="checkbox"/> Entretien du patrimoine familial |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Recommandations du conseiller agricole | <input type="checkbox"/> Autres raisons (préciser) _____ |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Épargne | _____ |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Diversification des revenus | |

2.2.2. Au cas où l'exploitant ne pratiquerait pas l'élevage, quelles en seraient les principales raisons ?

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Ne voit pas l'intérêt d'intégrer l'élevage dans son exploitation | <input type="checkbox"/> Manque d'agents techniques d'élevage pour fournir les conseils et les services vétérinaires |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Ne maîtrise pas les techniques d'élevage | <input type="checkbox"/> Indisponibilité des équipements et des intrants pour conduire l'activité |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Manque de moyens financiers | <input type="checkbox"/> Vol de bétail très courants dans la zone |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Manque de main d'œuvre pour la conduite des activités d'élevage | <input type="checkbox"/> Fortes mortalités des animaux |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Insuffisance de pâturage pour l'alimentation des animaux | <input type="checkbox"/> Autres (à préciser) _____ |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Manque d'espace pour le bâtiment d'élevage | _____ |

D2.2 Empirical model of constraints to the adoption of CSLP systems and practices

2.2.3 Quelles sont les principales contraintes rencontrées dans l'intégration de l'élevage aux activités de production végétales ?

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Manque d'aliments de bétail | <input type="checkbox"/> Manque de pâturage |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Manque de connaissances sur la conduite de l'élevage | <input type="checkbox"/> Manque d'agents techniques d'élevage pour fournir les conseils |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Conflits avec les agriculteurs | <input type="checkbox"/> Manque de moyens (charrettes, tricycles etc.) pour le transport du fumier |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Insécurité / vol de bétail | <input type="checkbox"/> Autres (à préciser) _____ |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Accès difficiles aux services vétérinaires et d'élevage | _____ |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Manque de piste à bétails | _____ |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Manque de moyens financiers | |

2.2.4 Au cas où l'exploitant aurait l'élevage pour activité principale et l'agriculture pour activité secondaire :

2.2.4.1 est-ce qu'il peut donner les principales motivations de l'intégration des productions végétales aux activités d'élevage ?

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Amélioration de la sécurité alimentaire | <input type="checkbox"/> Réduire la taille du cheptel et développer un élevage plus intensif |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Occuper et protéger le terrain contre l'accaparement | <input type="checkbox"/> Sédentarisation |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Diversifier les revenus | <input type="checkbox"/> Recommandation du conseiller d'élevage ou de l'agent vétérinaire |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Améliorer l'alimentation des animaux | <input type="checkbox"/> Autres (à préciser) _____ |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Valoriser le fumier produit par les animaux | _____ |

2.2.4.2 Quelles sont les principales contraintes rencontrées dans l'intégration des productions végétales aux activités d'élevage ?

- | | |
|--|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Accès difficiles aux conseil agricole | <input type="checkbox"/> Conflits avec les agriculteurs |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Manque de main d'œuvre | <input type="checkbox"/> Insécurité foncière |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Manque de connaissances techniques pour la conduite des activités agricoles | <input type="checkbox"/> Manque de terres |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Indisponibilité des intrants (semences, engrais etc.) | <input type="checkbox"/> Autres (à préciser) _____ |
| | _____ |
| | _____ |

2.3 Intégration des arbustes

2.3.1 L'exploitant plante/entretient-il des arbustes dans ses champs ? a) Oui b) Non

2.3.2 Si oui, Si non : allez à 2.3.3

2.3.2.1 Quelles sont les motivations de la plantation/entretien des arbustes dans les parcelles ?

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Amélioration de la fertilité des sols | <input type="checkbox"/> Suivi de l'exemple des parents, amis ou proches |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Alimentation humaine | <input type="checkbox"/> C'est le conseiller agricole qui a décidé |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Fourrages pour les animaux | <input type="checkbox"/> Autres raisons (à préciser) : _____ |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Pharmacopée | _____ |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Diversifier les revenus à travers la vente de la production | _____ |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Bénéficier des financements apportés par un projet | |

2.3.2.2 Quelles sont les principales espèces d'arbustes utilisées et les modalités de leur intégration ?

Nom local	Nom scientifique	Raisons choix*	Modalité d'intégration**	Densité (nbre de plants/ha)

Légende. * : 1) alimentation des animaux, (2) fertilité des sols, (3) alimentation humaine, (4) diversification des revenus, (5) pharmacopée, (6) sécurisation du foncier, (7) choix du projet ou de l'organisme d'appui, (8) autres (à préciser)

** : a) plantation à l'intérieur des champs, en association avec les cultures ; (b) plantation à la lisière des champs ; (c) création d'un parc spécifique d'arbustes, (d) autres

2.3.3 Quelles sont les principales difficultés rencontrées dans l'intégration des arbustes dans l'exploitation ?

- Manque des semences et/ou des plants
- Manque connaissances techniques sur la plantation et l'entretien des arbustes
- Manque de moyens financiers
- Insécurité foncière ou manque de terre
- Destruction des plants par les animaux
- Compétition avec les cultures
- Difficulté de mécaniser les travaux agricoles
- Contradiction avec les messages des conseillers agricoles (exp. promotion de la monoculture)
- Manque de conseil de la part des agents forestiers et des conseillers agricoles
- La réglementation non-adaptée (exp. autorisation de la vaine pâture, loi forestière très sévère en matière d'entretien de certaines espèces d'arbustes)
- Autres difficultés (à préciser) : _____

3/ Solutions endogènes et types d'appuis externes attendus pour renforcer l'intégration cultures ?

3.1 Avez-vous déjà développé des solutions aux difficultés majeures que vous rencontrez dans la conduite des systèmes intégrés ? a) oui b) non

3.2 Pensez-vous qu'un appui externe est nécessaire pour lever les contraintes? a) oui b) non

3.3. si oui, merci de compléter le tableau suivant :

	Principales difficultés rencontrées	Solutions apportées par le producteur	Types d'appuis externes attendus
Intégration de l'élevage ¹	- - ... - .		
Intégration de l'agriculture ²	- - ...		
Intégration des arbustes	- - -		

¹ Dans le cas où l'agriculture est l'activité principale

² Dans le cas où l'élevage est l'activité principale

3.4a/ avez-vous déjà participé des sensibilisations ou de formations sur l'intégration des cultures, des arbustes et de l'élevage (CAE) ? a) oui b) non

3.4.b si oui, préciser le thème de la formation et le nom de l'organisation qui l'avait dispensée :

3.4c/ Avez-vous les connaissances techniques nécessaires pour la mise en place et la conduite des systèmes intégrés CAE ? a) oui b) non

3.5/ Est-ce que les règles locales régissant la gestion des ressources naturelles (foncier, résidus de récolte etc.) sont favorables à la pratique des systèmes intégrés CAE ? a) oui b) non

3.6/ Est-ce que les conseillers agricoles promeuvent les systèmes intégrés CAE ? a) oui b) non

3.7/ Est-ce les agents d'élevage promeuvent les systèmes intégrés CAE ? a) oui b) non

3.8/ Est-ce les agents forestiers promeuvent les systèmes intégrés CAE ? a) oui b) non

3.9/ Au cas où vous recevez des conseils de la part des services techniques, est-ce que ces conseils sont adaptés et applicables votre situation ? a) oui b) non

3.10 Est-ce que l'exploitant a facilement accès aux services techniques quand il a besoin de connaissances, de conseil ou d'autres types d'appui sur les systèmes CAE ? a) oui b) non

4/ Perspectives

4.1 Est-ce que vous comptez renforcer l'intégration cultures-arbustes-élevage au sein de votre exploitation agricole au cours des prochaines années ? a) oui b) non

4.2a Est-ce que vous partagez avec d'autres producteurs vos connaissances sur les bénéfices et la manière de gérer les systèmes intégrés CSLP ? a) oui b) non

4.2b Si oui, a combien de personnes partagez-vous ces connaissances ? _____

4.2c Parmi ces personnes, quel est le pourcentage de ceux qui appliquent les connaissances partagées ? _____%

4.3 D'après vous, quelles sont les trois grandes mesures qu'il faudrait prendre pour promouvoir de l'intégration CAE ?

- a) _____
- b) _____
- c) _____

7.2 Guide d'entretien avec les personnels des services techniques (agriculture, élevage, foresterie)

- D'après vous, est-ce que les systèmes intégrés CAE sont important pour développement Agricole durable ? Merci de justifier votre réponse ?
- Est-ce que les politiques agro-sylvo-pastorales actuelles encouragent la mise en place des systèmes intégrés CAE ? si oui, quelles sont les actions concrètes qui sont menées dans ce sens ? Est-ce que ces actions rencontrent un succès ?
- Est-ce qu'il existerait une contradiction entre la mise en place des systèmes CAE et les orientations politiques et techniques actuelles ?
- Quelles sont d'après vous les principales contraintes systèmes CAE ? quelles sont les conséquences de ces difficultés ?
- Quelles mesures doivent être adoptées pour promouvoir avec succès les systèmes CAE ?

7.3 Appendix 2: List of people involved in data collection and preliminary analysis

Liste des personnes impliquées dans la collecte et la pré-analyse des données au Sénégal

Prénoms et noms	Fonction
Dr. Fatimata Binta Hassedine DIOUF	Coordnatrice des activités/Analyse et rapport
Abou Thiwdé SOW	Enquêteur et Superviseur/ analyse et rapport
Ibrahima DIOUF	Enquêteur
Mamadou GNING	Enquêteur
Pierre C. César DIEDHIOU	Enquêteur

Liste des personnes impliquées dans la collecte et la pré-analyse des données au Burkina Faso

N°	Nom (s) et Prénom (s)	Fonction	Rôle au cours de la mission
1.	KABORE Bruno	Chargé de programme RESCAR-AOC	Chef de mission / Enquêteur
2.	ZOUNDI Gniessebingba	Stagiaires INERA/Géotechnique	Enquêteur
3.	COMPAORE S. J. Mukassa	Stagiaires INERA/Géotechnique	Enquêteur
4.	BAZIE Bapio	Producteur semencier Sanguié	Enquêteur
5.	YAMEOGO Sylvain	Animateur UPPA Boulkiemde	Enquêteur
6.	KOURAOGO Alexandre	Animateur CPF	Mobilisation et soutien-conseil
7.	KAMA Louise	Animatrice CPF	Mobilisation et soutien-conseil
8.	ZONGO Jérémie	CVD Villy	Mobilisation
9.	KABRE Xavier	CVD Saria	Mobilisation
10.	OUEDRAOGO Ablassé	CVD Ramongo-Tangin	Mobilisation
11.	KABORE Issouf	CVD Tampelga	Mobilisation

7.4 Key shrubs and trees species used in CSLP systems in Saria sites

Local name	Scientific name
Baganda	<i>Piliostigma reticulatum</i>
Cassia	<i>Acacia polyacantha</i>
Citron	<i>Citrus limon</i>
Eucalyptus	<i>Eucalyptus globulus</i>
Gaanka	<i>Diospyros mespiliformis</i>
Goyake	<i>Psidium guajava</i>
Kadga	<i>Detarium microcarpum</i>
Kieghaligha	<i>Balanites aegyptiaca</i>
kouinkouiga	<i>Ficus thonningi</i>
Kuka	<i>Khaya senegalensis</i>
Mang-tuga	<i>Mangifera indica</i>
Moringa	<i>Moringa oleifera</i>
Muguna	<i>Ziziphus mucronata</i>
Neem	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>
Noabga	<i>Sclerocarya birrea</i>
Orange	<i>Citrus sinensis</i>
Papaye	<i>Carica papaya</i>
Pegnenga	<i>Acacia nilotica</i>
Pelega	<i>Securidaca longepedunculata</i>
Pusga	<i>Tamarindus indica</i>
Roanga	<i>Parkia biglobosa</i>
Saabga	<i>Lannea microcarpa</i>
Siiga	<i>Anogeissus leiocarpus</i>
Tâanga	<i>Vitellaria paradoxa</i>
Toeega	<i>Adansonia digitata</i>
Voaaka	<i>Bombax costatum</i>
Wegda	<i>Saba senegalensis</i>
Willinwiiga	<i>Guiera senegalensis</i>
Zaanga	<i>Faidherbia albida</i>